

The National Library of the Netherlands (*Koninklijke Bibliotheek, KB*) applies the power of the written word to help make the Netherlands smarter, more skilled and more creative. Our challenge is to continue to develop as a cutting-edge knowledge institution in an ever-changing digital information landscape. This will ensure that the national library collection can remain sustainable, visible and usable in the future. To achieve this aim, we have identified five themes in this Research Agenda on which we plan to focus in the next four years. We want to engage in dialogue with our network partners in the worlds of science and scholarship, heritage and business, in order to further develop our knowledge of these themes and make them applicable for practical solutions. The digital transformation that our organisation is experiencing is leading to changes. Our Research Agenda will help us to make well-founded policy decisions and to identify the themes and issues that will affect the KB in the medium and long term.

EXPERTS & TRENDS

This Research Agenda has been developed after numerous discussions with experts within and outside the KB. As a result of these discussions, we have identified six trends that recur in each of the research themes. These trends are: 1) applicability of **artificial intelligence**, 2) use of and reflection on the use of **big data**, 3) increasing importance of **privacy & security**, 4) changes in the **publication landscape**, 5) providing greater **accountability** for activities as a (semi-)public organisation, and 6) the further development of the **self-reliant society**.

FIVE THEMES

INFORMATION SOCIETY: WHAT IS THE KB'S ROLE IN THE GLOBAL INFORMATION SOCIETY?

PUBLICATIONS: HOW DO WE DEFINE 'THE WRITTEN WORD'? WHAT WILL BE THE PUBLICATIONS OF THE FUTURE?

ACCESS & SHARING: HOW CAN WE IMPROVE OUR COLLECTIONS? HOW AND WHERE WILL WE MAKE THEM AVAILABLE?

CUSTOMERS: WHAT DO OUR CUSTOMERS DO WITH OUR SERVICES, PROGRAMMES AND COLLECTIONS?

IMPACT: HOW DO WE KNOW WHAT IMPACT OUR ACTIVITIES HAVE ON SOCIETY?

INFORMATION SOCIETY

THEME 1: INFORMATION SOCIETY

WHAT IS A NATIONAL LIBRARY'S ROLE, BOTH DIGITAL AND PHYSICAL, IN A CHANGING INFORMATION SOCIETY?

People absorb information all the time, in all different kinds of ways. In their quest for information, they shift effortlessly between the various online **platforms**: moving from Google to Delpher, from Wikipedia to Facebook, searching for literature at DBNL.nl or borrowing an e-book from a library website. At the same time, the way information is produced is changing. Academics publish their work as **open-access** articles and publishers of books, newspapers and magazines also distribute their digital content via **different media and platforms**. Alongside these developments in the digital domain, people still need human contact: major online stores like Amazon and Coolblue are opening up outlets in large cities and cafés are increasingly being used as places to meet and work.

PUBLICATIONS

THEME 2: PUBLICATIONS

WHICH MEANS OF COMMUNICATION DO WE CONSIDER TO BE PUBLICATIONS?

The written word is the starting point for what the KB does. But the key question is: how do you define the written word in today's world? In the past, publications were limited to books and magazines, but the written word now takes many forms. Digital publications have taken a leap forward: they are posted online, shared, linked to data and reused. This raises the question of what means of communications we actually consider to be publications. Is every online blog post a publication? What about **multimedia e-books** or **enhanced academic publications**? Out of all of the wide-ranging publications that appear on a daily basis, what should be preserved for eternity? Is it enough to limit ourselves to websites that are representative of the time in which we are living?

The question arises: how can we preserve these publications in a sustainable manner and provide access to them in all their different forms. We need to make well-argued, careful and responsible choices. How do we ensure that the data we store remains **FAIR** (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) – even when today's technology eventually becomes obsolete?

ACCESS AND SHARING

THEME 3: ACCESS AND SHARING

As well as sustainably preserving our collections, we want to ensure that we provide our customers optimal access to them. This involves improving the quality of digital content (in ways a computer can interpret it), creating metadata, enriching content and distributing it.

HOW DO WE IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF OUR DIGITAL CONTENT?

With the help of optical character and layout recognition ([OCR and OLR](#)), computers are capable of reading scans of newspaper articles.

We are now focusing on [deep-learning techniques](#) to improve our OCR, enabling computers to be trained to recognise and correct their own mistakes.

HOW DO WE CREATE (SEMI-)AUTOMATIC METADATA FOR SMARTER AND RICHER CONTENT DESCRIPTIONS?

Thanks to techniques from [artificial intelligence](#), such as [language technology](#) and image recognition, our computers are increasingly capable of interpreting texts. They are now able to identify characters and genres in a publication and add this information to the publication's metadata. This data has huge potential because in the future, it will enable us to more effectively help our customers to find content in which they are interested.

Currently, computers still recognise and interpret texts based on instructions from humans. However, the next step will involve computers doing this themselves and start to give [recommendations](#).

In addition, we can use [image recognition](#) to identify people, objects and subjects in images. However, poor quality scans make this more difficult because of low resolution.

HOW CAN WE PROVIDE SMARTER ACCESS TO OUR CONTENT WITH THE HELP OF CITIZEN SCIENTISTS?

Major advances have been made by using members of the public ([citizen scientists](#)) to train computers. But with the sheer size of the data we have, we need to use and develop even smarter methods: computers must be given a nudge to enable them to take on human tasks.

[Recognition of handwriting](#), for example, is something that we still have people do. We have large numbers of good quality digital manuscripts and numerous experts, including palaeography specialists of medieval manuscripts. How can we deploy experts and the public to enable even smarter access to these kinds of sources?

HOW CAN WE ENRICH OUR COLLECTIONS, CONNECT THEM TO EACH OTHER AND PRESENT THEM TOGETHER TO OUR CUSTOMERS?

New developments of the semantic web, [linked data](#) and knowledge databases like [Wikipedia](#) offer the opportunity to identify and enhance [entities](#) (e.g. people, locations and buildings), enabling the user to find all the information he or she is looking for as quickly as possible.

This can be done by adding additional stages of information to the users' query and thus channelling the user's question. By connecting the data from various collections, we aim to offer our user an answer that is as complete as possible.

WHICH PLATFORMS CAN BE USED TO DISTRIBUTE DIGITAL CONTENT?

Which media and [platforms](#) will be used to communicate in twenty years' time? What developments can we see on the horizon and how can we anticipate on these in order to offer our content on the [consumer platforms](#) of the future?

CUSTOMER

THEME 4: CUSTOMER

HOW CAN WE CONDUCT RESPONSIBLE AND IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS OF OUR CUSTOMERS' BEHAVIOUR?

For several years, the KB has been responsible for the public library system. We focused on identifying the user needs of these new customer groups and made good progress in this. However, it becomes more complicated when we try to answer the question of what our customers actually do with our services. This involves the analysis of their user behaviour. We aim to conduct in-depth analysis of what people search for online, but also which physical books and e-books they borrow. We have [Big Data](#)-like datasets that we can use to help our customers, but we want to do this in a way that is [ethically responsible](#). First and foremost, we want to offer a safe and reliable environment such as is being developed within the [Responsible Data Science](#) consortium, that developed the [FACT](#) principles of Fairness, Accuracy, Confidentiality and Transparency

IMPACT

THEME 5: IMPACT

HOW DO WE DEMONSTRATE OUR ADDED VALUE AND MEASURE IMPACT ON SOCIETY?

Finally, in the years ahead we will focus on measuring the long-term impact of our activities. This is far from easy: how do you demonstrate your [added value](#), how do you measure your [impact on society](#)? We are aware of our outreach within the Dutch population: how many people use our services and how satisfied they are. But we do not know if this will change society in the long term. We aim to develop [indicators](#) that can measure the [impact](#) of the KB's contribution to a sustainable society over the long term.

IN SHORT

IN SHORT...

The KB is continuously moving and developing fast. We have [a unique quantity of data](#) of a very high quality at our disposal, we are experts in [connecting digital collections](#) and in actively bringing these connections to [various platforms](#) so that everyone can use them. In addition, we aim to understand the [behaviour](#) of our users in a responsible way in order to achieve maximum [impact](#). We also have a lot to offer academics, scientists and researchers and are happy to share knowledge and experience with our network. At the same time, we intend to engage in discussion with other experts and partners about their new developments and improvements to enable us to reinforce each other and take concerted action.

If you are interested in collaboration with the KB, please contact Martijn Kleppe, National Library of the Netherlands Director of Research: martijn.kleppe@kb.nl For more information about the research agenda, see www.kb.nl/researchagenda

With its Research Agenda, the KB aims to align itself with similar national agendas and policy plans, such as the Creative Industry Top Sector's Knowledge and Innovation Agenda 2018-2021, the policy plan of the alliance of university libraries and the National Library of the Netherlands (UKB), the National Open Science Plan and the Digital Society Research Agenda of the Netherlands Association of Universities (VSNU) as much as possible. The agenda builds on the activities of CLARIAH and the activities and plans of the Digital Heritage Network (NDE), as expressed in the National Digital Heritage Strategy. Finally, the themes link in with the routes of the Dutch National Research Agenda, with a focus on big data, the living past, resilient societies and youth. At European level, we aim to connect with the Horizon 2020 programme and its successor and the Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage (JPIC).